

Fig. 1. Titration curves of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-sulphafurazole.

Acknowledgement

The authors record their sincere thanks to Dr. D. G. Vartak, B. A. R. C., Bombay for valuable suggestions.

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Conductance of KCl and NaCl in Sucrose + Water, Glucose + Water and Urea + Water Mixtures at Different Temperatures

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Manuscript received 4 February 1982, accepted 21 July 1982

STRUCTURAL interactions in ternary system comprising electrolyte-solvent-nonelectrolyte are gaining special attention in recent years. It has been

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observed that nonelectrolyte molecules interact with the ions of the electrolytes in solution¹⁻³. Several polyhydroxy compounds are known to interact with electrolytes in solutions^{1,4}. Definite adducts of many carbohydrates with salts and hydrated oxides of alkali and alkaline earth metals have also been reported^{5,6}. Conductance of electrolyte solutions in the presence of nonelectrolytes have been measured by several workers¹⁻³. The changes in conductance of carbohydrate-electrolyte solutions¹⁰ was attributed to the obstruction of electrical migration of ions by the environmental nonelectrolyte entities^{11,12}.

In the present communication, the ion-solvent interaction of KCl and NaCl have been studied from conductivity data at weight percent of nonelectrolyte (sucrose, glucose) + water (5, 10, 15 and 20) mixtures at 30, 35, 40 and 45° and urea + water at 30 and 35°.

Materials and methods :

The salts used were of E. Merck 'Extra Pure' grade. Sucrose, glucose and urea were of B.D.H. AnalaR grade. The methods for preparation of the solvents and solutions and of measurements were the same as reported earlier¹³. Conductance measurement was of an accuracy of ± 2 in 1000. The concentration range was from 0.01 to 0.001 equiv/lit. Studies above 35° could not be performed in case of urea + water because of hydrolysis.

Results and Discussion

The equivalent conductivity of KCl and NaCl investigated at weight percent of nonelectrolyte (sucrose, glucose and urea) + water mixtures (5, 10, 15 and 20) are found to be linear with $C^{1/2}$ in the concentration range 0.01 to 0.001 mol lit⁻¹. This indicates that the salts are completely ionised. The limiting equivalent conductivity, Λ° , for KCl and NaCl at different compositions and at different temperatures obtained from the usual extrapolation procedure are given in Table 1 along with the values in aqueous solution¹⁴.

From the determined Λ° values, the theoretical slope, S_T , of the plot of Λ vs $C^{1/2}$ at 35° for KCl and NaCl at different solvent compositions has been obtained and compared with the observed slope, S (Table 2). The S value is found to be greater than S_T , which indicates that the observed conductance is less than that of the theoretical value. This difference is of the order : sucrose + water > urea + water > glucose + water, which indicates the structure breaking order also.

The Walden product, $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$, has been usually employed to study ion-solvent interaction in solution from the conductivity data. $\Lambda^\circ \eta_0$ of both KCl and NaCl at different temperatures and at different solvent compositions are given in Table 3. The results show that it is maximum in case of glucose +

NOTES

TABLE-1
 $\Delta/\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$

Temp. Mass fraction of nonelectrolyte	Sucrose + water				Glucose + water				Urea + water	
	30	35	40	45	30	35	40	45	30	35
	KCl									
5	160.00	174.8	189.0	202.8	160.0	174.2	186.6	203.0	167.6	181.8
10	150.90	159.9	173.2	186.4	150.0	163.3	176.2	188.3	165.0	177.0
15	135.8	145.6	159.6	171.2	136.7	147.0	161.1	172.6	162.4	176.0
20	121.0	133.4	144.0	154.2	123.5	134.9	145.6	156.7	151.8	163.0
	NaCl									
5	139.5	153.8	169.0	181.6	141.4	153.4	169.0	183.3	149.0	161.8
10	129.4	142.8	154.0	167.6	131.5	144.4	156.2	169.2	145.0	153.8
15	114.2	135.6	146.8	156.6	116.4	127.6	138.8	149.6	137.8	150.6
20	103.2	113.8	123.9	134.6	105.4	115.7	126.6	137.0	130.4	142.9

* values at 25°C

TABLE 2—SLOPE VALUES (at 35° only)/mol^{-1/2}cm^{7/2}

	5% Sucrose		10% Sucrose		15% Sucrose		20% Sucrose	
	S	S _T	S	S _T	S	S _T	S	S _T
KCl	104.2	99.4	105.2	99.6	106.3	99.8	106.9	100.2
NaCl	100.9	95.2	101.4	96.2	103.3	97.4	103.4	98.3
	5% Glucose		10% Glucose		15% Glucose		20% Glucose	
KCl	102.7	99.4	103.6	99.5	104.6	99.9	105.6	100.3
NaCl	99.6	96.2	99.9	96.2	100.8	97.4	101.6	98.2
	5% Urea		10% Urea		15% Urea		20% Urea	
KCl	103.00	99.4	104.2	99.5	105.5	99.9	106.2	100.3
NaCl	100.40	96.0	100.8	96.0	101.2	97.3	102.6	97.8

TABLE 3— $\Delta^{\circ}/\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ P}$

Temp. Mass fraction of nonelectrolyte	Sucrose + water				Glucose + water				Urea + water	
	30	35	40	45	30	35	40	45	30	35
	KCl									
5	1.967	2.098	2.107	2.224	2.464	2.917	3.467	4.155	2.312	2.727
10	2.327	2.440	2.643	2.790	2.865	3.350	4.035	4.726	2.492	2.938
15	2.729	2.822	3.093	3.201	3.527	4.201	5.333	5.558	2.598	3.027
20	3.025	3.308	3.470	3.667	3.693	4.357	5.169	6.049	2.778	3.195
	NaCl									
5	1.716	1.846	1.884	2.017	2.177	2.562	3.160	3.739	2.056	2.427
10	1.992	2.171	2.325	2.514	2.511	2.959	3.577	4.246	2.189	2.636
15	2.284	2.437	2.586	2.741	3.003	3.560	4.305	4.817	2.205	2.605
20	2.580	2.822	2.986	3.203	3.151	3.725	4.494	5.288	2.386	2.801

TABLE 4—DIFFERENCE IN $\Delta/\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$

Temp. Mass fraction of nonelectrolyte	Sucrose + water				Glucose + water				Urea + water	
	30	35	40	45	30	35	40	45	30	35
5	20.5	21.0	20.0	21.2	18.6	20.8	17.6	19.7	18.6	20.0
10	21.5	17.1	19.2	18.8	18.5	18.9	20.2	19.1	20.0	18.2
15	21.6	20.0	23.8	24.6	20.3	19.4	22.3	23.0	24.4	25.4
20	17.8	19.6	20.1	19.6	18.1	19.2	19.0	19.7	21.4	20.1

water and minimum in case of sucrose + water, urea + water being in between the two. Hence, the ion-solvent interaction is of the order :

sucrose + water > urea + water > glucose + water.

A better insight of the ion-solvent interaction can be obtained if the differences in the conductivity of KCl-NaCl at different compositions and at different temperatures be compared. These differences are recorded in Table 4. The differences are

not constant. The deviation from constancy in case of sucrose + water is maximum and least in case of glucose + water, whereas urea + water is in between the two. The more the deviation, the greater is the ion-solvent interaction¹⁵. So the order of ion-solvent interaction is sucrose + water > urea + water > glucose + water.

The above observations can be explained as follows. Sucrose contains more hydroxy groups than d-glucose and these hydroxy groups present in the compounds participate in the formation of hydrogen bonds with water molecules and hence the water structure breaks. Sucrose, therefore, is a stronger structure breaker than glucose. As regards urea, it can be said that urea is alkaline in water and acts both as a proton donor and acceptor, and hence in the mixture of urea and water, the structure is likely to be broken. Secondly, due to keto-enol tautomerism in solution urea may contain one hydroxy group which participates in the formation of hydrogen bond with water molecules and structure breaking is observed.

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Synthesis of Some 5-Arylazopyrimidine Derivatives

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Manuscript received 14 June 1978, revised 28 January 1982,
accepted 25 August 1982

IN continuation of our work on the synthesis of 5-arylazopyrimidine derivatives of biological interest¹, we report here the synthesis of three

more series of compounds, namely 2-amino-5-arylo-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines (I), 5-arylo-2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidines (II) and 5-arylo-4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidines (III).

All the compounds (I, II and III) were synthesized in excellent yields by the reaction of different aryldiazonium chlorides with appropriately substituted pyrimidine derivatives. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by their elemental analysis and ir spectra (bands in the region 1630-1590 cm⁻¹ due to -N=N-stretching). The arylazo group at position-5 was further confirmed by reducing three arylazo derivatives (one from each series) with Zn and AcOH. 2-Amino-4-hydroxy-6-methyl-5-phenylazopyrimidine (I, X=Y=H), on reduction, afforded 2,5-diamino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine while II (X=Y=H) and III (X=Y=H) gave 5-amino-2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine and 5-amino-4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidine, respectively.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillary in a sulphuric acid bath and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded on a Beckman IR-20 spectrophotometer as nujol mulls.

2-Amino-4-hydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine², 2,4-dihydroxy-6-methylpyrimidine³ and 4,6-dimethyl-2-hydroxypyrimidine⁴ were prepared by the methods described in literature and coupled with different aryl diazonium chlorides according to the method reported earlier¹. All the compounds were crystallized from DMF-ethanol mixture. The characteristics of compounds belonging to series I, II and III have been listed in Tables 1, 2 and 3, respectively.

TABLE 1—CHARACTERISTICS OF 2-AMINO-5-ARYLAZO-4-HYDROXY-6-METHYLPYRIMIDINES (I)

Sl. No.	X,Y	m.p. °C	Yield %	Analysis %	
				Calcd.	Found
1.	H	297 ^d	75	N, 30.57	30.24
2.	2-CH ₃	302	52	N, 28.80	28.64
3.	3-CH ₃	316 ^d	65	N, 28.80	28.68
4.	4-CH ₃	299	48	N, 28.80	28.39
5.	2-OCH ₃	307 ^d	63	N, 27.03	27.13
6.	3-OCH ₃	283	72	N, 27.03	26.92
7.	4-OCH ₃	298 ^d	70	N, 27.03	26.92
8.	4-OC ₂ H ₅	206	50	N, 25.64	25.50
9.	2-Cl	128	78	Cl, 13.47	13.28
10.	4-Cl	288	80	Cl, 13.47	13.26
11.	2-Br	266	76	Br, 26.00	26.10
12.	4-Br	245	74	Br, 26.00	25.90
13.	2-NO ₂	301	80	N, 30.56	30.49
14.	3-NO ₂	314 ^d	81	N, 30.56	30.46
15.	4-NO ₂	319 ^d	81	N, 30.56	27.23
16.	3,5-(CH ₃) ₂	315	61	N, 27.23	27.23
17.	2,4-(Cl) ₂	299	65	Cl, 23.82	23.78

d = melts with decomposition.

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